

Auditing Bias: Detecting and Quantifying Bias in Search Query Suggestions for US Politicians

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1. Background and Related Work

Search engines serve as primary information gateways, particularly in sensitive domains such as politics (Ray, 2020; Edelman, 2022). Search Query Suggestions, the dynamically generated prompts appearing as users type, guide search behavior (Niu & Kelly, 2014; Cai & de Rijke, 2016). Query suggestions are prone to contain various biases, potentially influencing opinion formation (Epstein & Robertson, 2015; Epstein et al., 2024) and reinforcing societal inequities (Noble, 2018). Bias in query suggestions is particularly critical when searching for political topics or real existing people. The former can have an impact on actual politics by influencing political opinion formation, while the latter can present certain groups of people unequally, unfairly, or potentially in a defamatory manner. Despite the growing awareness of algorithmic bias (Kulshrestha et al., 2019), query suggestions remain understudied compared to search results, partly due to challenges like data sparsity, lack of context, and the subjective nature of bias itself (Bonart et al., 2019; Haak & Schaer, 2022). Existing research has often focused on topical or gender bias (Mertens et al., 2019; Haak & Schaer, 2021, 2022), typically using clustering, frequency counts, or categorizations. While valuable, these methods often struggle to capture the perceived impact or the severity of the identified bias. Perception-aware metrics, such as Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (nDCG), were introduced to account for suggestion rank (Haak & Schaer, 2021), acknowledging differential perceivability (Hofmann et al., 2014). Recently, a pairwise comparison approach leveraging large language models (LLMs) has been used to quantify bias in query suggestions, achieving an effectiveness comparable to human annotation (Haak et al., 2024). However, this approach has not yet been applied to real-world search query datasets or in conjunction with perception-aware bias quantification. This paper aims to address these gaps by investigating bias in query suggestions for prominent US politicians, employing LLMs for nuanced analysis, framing disparities through group fairness, and integrating a quantitative measure of bias severity using pairwise comparison and Elo scoring (Haak et al., 2024), which enables a more granular understanding than prior approaches.

2. Methodology

Our methodology encompasses dataset creation, LLM-driven bias categorization for group fairness analysis, and bias severity quantification using pairwise comparison and Elo rating. Figure 1 offers a schematic overview of the full workflow.

Figure 1: Overview of methodology.

2.1. Dataset

We utilize a large dataset of query suggestions collected from Google and Bing for the names of the 352 most prominent US politicians (YouGov 2025). The dataset was collected using recursive algorithm interrogation (RAI) techniques (Haak & Schaer, 2022, 2023; Robertson et al., 2019). Initial suggestions for each politician’s name were retrieved. Root queries were also expanded by appending letters ‘a’ through ‘z’ to capture broader suggestion sets. Data collection was conducted without user profiles using Google Colab to minimize personalization effects.

2.2. Group Fairness Analysis: Bias Categorization & Comparison

Group fairness demands that members of groups be treated equally, independent of their group affiliations. Applied to query suggestions, this means that to establish group fairness, no members of a specific categorical group of meta-attributes (e.g., gender: male/female, party affiliation: Democrat/Republican, popularity, age, etc.) should be over-exposed to bias or receive qualitatively different suggestions. To investigate biases and fairness in query suggestions for US politicians, we analyze the distribution of query suggestion biases across several dimensions, drawing from prior work (Haak & Schaer, 2021; Spinde et al., 2023). Topical bias is assessed by categorizing query suggestions as ‘Political’, ‘Private’, or ‘Neutral/Other’. Political stance bias identifies suggestions as ‘Left-leaning’, ‘Right-leaning’, or ‘Neutral’. Ideological stance bias identifies ‘Authoritarian’, ‘Libertarian’, or ‘Neutral’ suggestions. We leverage an LLM for this context-aware, scalable classification.

2.3. Bias Severity Quantification

We adapt the methodology presented in (Haak et al., 2024), built upon the ARTS framework for relative assessment using pairwise comparison and Elo scoring (Engelmann et al., 2024), to quantify the perceived severity of suggestions identified as potentially biased. The process involves two steps. First, an LLM performs 24 rounds of pairwise comparisons: given two potentially biased query suggestions, it determines which exhibits bias that is more prone to cognitively or emotionally affect a user. To mitigate positional bias, the order of queries is randomized for each comparison. Second, the outcomes of pairwise comparisons feed into an Elo rating system (Good, 1955). This system assigns a score penalty or gain based on the expected outcome deducted from the scores before the comparison. Elo scores thus reflect the relative bias severity of each query suggestion compared to others. In matchmaking, pairs are assigned based on similar scores. The resulting scores, in conjunction with perception-aware weighting metrics (nDCG), allow for analysis of bias severity. The proportional distribution of quantified biases and topic distributions is then compared between the groups of meta-attributes using statistical tests to identify significant disparities that may indicate fairness issues within the groups for both search engines.

2.4. Observations and Implications

Analyses suggest potential systematic differences in the query suggestions presented for politicians of different parties and in other groups of meta-attributes. For example, on both Google and Bing, Republicans receive a higher percentage of biased suggestions than Democrats. However, the average severity of bias is significantly higher for Democrats than for Republicans. Similar significant disparities were found for gender, with male politicians receiving a higher percentage of biased suggestions but female politicians facing slightly more severe bias on average. We also observed positive correlations between a politician's fame and the likelihood of receiving biased suggestions. The detection and quantification of such biases in query suggestions carry significant implications. Since query suggestions are largely derived from aggregated user search queries, biases observed within them can serve as a proxy, reflecting prevailing societal interests, curiosities, stereotypes, and potentially, societal biases regarding political figures. Studying these patterns offers a lens into collective public perception and information-seeking behavior, contributing to understanding the complex interplay between society and the search engines embedded within it. Analyzing how these biases manifest and differ across platforms and groups is crucial for promoting fairness and transparency online. The methodology and results presented in this work enable a more comprehensive search engine bias audit and a deeper understanding of the dynamics in political query suggestions.

3. References

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